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Non-surgical removal of shoulder calcification

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After (a week later)

The patient is a 49-year-old female who was treated for frozen shoulder by CellSonic VIPP at [Ravina Hospital](#) in Chennai in India. No drugs or anaesthetic were used. She had been suffering from shoulder pain and lack of full movement for almost three years. The protocol was 200 Pulses at Energy Level 5 for 8 days. The patient sat upright for the treatments. Each

session took only two minutes. Normally for cases like this the protocol is 1,000 pulses at energy level 7 and only one treatment is needed whilst in Ravina the treatment was spread over eight days. The patient was expecting open surgery to remove the calcification as this was recommended by the orthopaedic surgeon. However, the patient and surgeon were

persuaded by CellSonic India that surgery was unnecessary, expensive and would have side effects along with the time taken for an inflicted wound to heal. The physiotherapist carried out the treatment resulting in the calcification dispersing within one week. The patient remains well without pain and now has full use of her arm and hand.

References

1. <https://www.ravinahospital.com/wound-and-pain-management-clinic-in-chennai.html>
2. <http://www.cellsonic-medical.com/pain.htm#> (see video)